

SPECIFIC FEATURES OF AFFIXES IN CHINESE AND
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ABSTRACT

This scientific article studies the specific features of the formation of military technical terms through the affixation method. The Chinese language, with its rich history and unique language structure, presents an attractive domain for the study of military terminology. This article examines the historical development, linguistic characteristics, and contemporary trends in the use of military technical terms in the Chinese language, sheds light on the importance of language in military communication and the cultural significance embedded in these terms.

Introduction

The presence of suffixes is an important factor in the formation of the systematic nature of Chinese vocabulary. The use of suffixes in Chinese often follows certain rules and principles that form the necessary basis of the Chinese vocabulary system. For example, Chinese suffixes often have fixed positions and functions, which manifests the structure of Chinese vocabulary with a certain regularity and systematicity. The scientific works of such Russian scientists as A. Dragunov, N. Korotov, V. Solntsev, B. Isayenko, N. Solntseva, S. Yakhontov, A. Semenas should be recognized as the basis for the theories of word formation in Chinese. The study of word formation in Chinese by affixation, as an important area of linguistics, requires in-depth research using various methods and approaches. With the development of science and technology, and the development of linguistic theories, researchers are constantly trying new methods to gain a broader and deeper understanding of Chinese suffixes.

Among the modern Chinese scholars, 刘汉武, 赵吉云, 富丽, 汪家靓, 罗晨, 李蓓, 曾立英, 冯建奎, 赵艳平, 石月姣, 高狄, 张爱武, 朱亚军, 沈光浩, 王洁, 李茵幽, and 李美子 have studied word formation through affixation in their scientific research. The theory of word formation in modern Chinese has been thoroughly studied in Uzbek by S. Hashimova. Traditional textual research is the most fundamental method. By sorting and analyzing ancient books and documents, we can trace the historical evolution of suffixes, study their origin and development. Although this method requires a lot of time and effort, it provides us with rich historical materials and helps to create a comprehensive basis for the evolution of suffixes.

The term affix in the Uzbek language is derived from the Latin word "affixus" and means "attached". The Chinese term affix 缀 - means "stitched, decorated", and in linguistics it performs the function of affixation.

Sinologist, professor S. Hashimova, in her monograph "Reduplication, Affixation and Conversion in Modern Chinese", approving the opinion of F.F. Fortunatov, divided affixes into prefix 前缀, infix- 中缀, interfix- 间缀, transfix, confix, circumfix, ambifix, and provided a detailed scientific explanation of 25 types of affixation methods. Some of the lexical units in the Uzbek language undergo semantic changes over time due to circumstances. Unlike Chinese, the Uzbek language undergoes significant phonetic changes. Over time, some words become affixed suffixes. We have observed that military-technical terms in the Uzbek language are formed on the basis of certain forms of affixes. Linguistic units that can act both as words and as additions differ from formal affixes, which are called affixoids.

Conclusion

In the Uzbek language, affixoids are less common in military-technical terms, and in Chinese they are more productive. In the Uzbek language, affixes that are added after are called suffixoids, and affixes that are added before are called prefixoids. In the Uzbek language, there are also many affixes adopted from other languages in the affix system. In military-technical terms, noun-forming affixes predominate.

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